

Analysis of Nursing Services on Satisfaction Health Insurance Provider Agency Patients

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Abstract:-

Background: One of the successes of public services such as health and nursing services in a hospital or health center is through the level of patient satisfaction, with high patient satisfaction reflecting the good quality of medical services in the public sector. **Purpose:** It is known that the analysis of nursing services on BPJS health patient satisfaction. **Methods:** This research is an analytic cross-sectional study in which the sample selection was purposive sampling with univariate and bivariate data analysis. The research period was September-December 2022. The sample for this study was 62 outpatients. **Results:** The results of this study showed that the majority of patients rated good nursing services 51.6% of 62 respondents, while the patient satisfaction level of 62 respondents was 72.6%. **there is a significant relationship between the level of satisfaction with nursing services (P -value = 0.038). **Suggestion:** by obtaining meaningful results for nursing services to maintain their services and always maintain the quality of service so that services to patients are more meaningful and of higher quality so that patients feel satisfied, when patients feel satisfied this can help patients in treatment recover quickly because they feel served and handled immediately, of course, will feel satisfied / relieved with the nursing services provided.**

Keywords:- Nursing services, satisfaction, patient satisfaction Social Security Administration Agency/BPJS Health.

I. INTRODUCTION

Healthy Indonesia 2025 aims to realize quality health services, which will increase public demand for quality health services because consumers can choose the type and quality of health services they want, as well as health services in emergencies and disasters. All of these health services are carried out under the standards and ethics of the nursing profession, (Department of Health 2009).

In developing the world of nursing in the future, nursing services need to get top priority in order to be able to answer future challenges. The direction of development demands an arrangement of the nursing service delivery system by supporting the improvement of the quality of nursing education providers, from the tertiary level of nursing education so that they can carry out their roles and functions optimally to improve their professional performance through the quality of nursing care, (Maria, 2017)

Concern about providing the best service is the meaning of excellent service. Excellent service can be found in community health centers, hereinafter abbreviated as Puskesmas. Puskesmas aims to treat someone to achieve the best health (Barat, 2018). Health development can be achieved through basic health services, namely the Puskesmas, (Decree of the Minister of Health number 128 of 2004). Puskesmas is the Technical Implementation Unit of the District/City Health Office which is responsible for the implementation of health service development in one or part of the area. Puskesmas is the primary health service for all who live in their working area.

Patient satisfaction compares the expected performance with the reality received. According to Subiroso (2011), Patient satisfaction is a subjective value of the quality of services provided, meanwhile, according to Syafrudin (2011), Patient satisfaction is a reality but is often overlooked as an indicator of service quality with the wants, needs, and expectations of society. Wijono (1996) According to him, satisfaction is the productivity of health services assessed by patients, which is called a service quality.

Improving the quality of the Indonesian health sector is carried out through various approaches including quality control, quality control teams in various government and private hospitals, integrated quality control, and integrated quality management (*Total Quality Management/TQM*). The most important measure of quality is not price or cost, but compliance with established standards. Likewise, an item or service is said to be of good quality if the item or service is not defective according to existing standards. (Bustami, 2011).

To support this, it is necessary to reorganize educational development in a quality-influential/medical manner, the nursing distribution system must be rearranged so that the application of different graduation classes can be applied appropriately. The essence of the nursing profession is the provision of professional care to the community. (Sitaurus, 2006).

Based on this background, the researcher wanted to conduct a study "Analysis of nursing services on patient satisfaction of the Social Security Administration Agency, which will be abbreviated as (BPJS) health"

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a quantitative analytic research method with a cross-sectional approach where the independent variable and the dependent variable are measured/observed only once or all at the same time.

The sample of this study was all BPJS patients who were on outpatient treatment, from a total population of 165 respondents, 62 respondents were taken as a sample

The technique used in this study was purposive sampling, namely sampling based on certain reasoning made by the researchers themselves based on the characteristics or characteristics of the population that were known to the researchers, while the research was conducted between September and December 2022.

A. Research Ethics

Each patient who was sampled was first asked if they wanted to participate without being forced, then asked to sign an informed consent as a procedure in the research process. The researcher guarantees the confidentiality of the patient's identity. Photo documentation is only used as research material, not published/exhibited other than for research purposes.

B. Data Processing Procedures

Information obtained from interviews or observations using research instruments will be processed using the following steps: Editing where the results of the research questionnaire are obtained, then checking again whether there are questions that have not been filled in by the respondents or are all complete, then the number of respondents' answers is calculated and then grouped according to those contained in the operational definition

No	Nursing Services	Amount (n)	Percentage (%)
1	Well	50	80,6
2	Bad	12	19,4
Total		62	100

Table 1: Distribution of Outpatient BPJS Patient Nursing Services

Based on Table 1, it can be interpreted that most of 80.6% of the total 62 respondents to good nursing services

b) Characteristics of the frequency distribution of outpatient BPJS patient satisfaction

In this study, patient satisfaction variables were divided into two categories, namely satisfied and dissatisfied. The frequency table is as follows:

No	Nursing Services	Amount (n)	Percentage (%)
1	Satisfied	59	79,0
2	Not satisfied	13	21,0
Total		62	100

Table 2: Distribution of Nursing Service Satisfaction for BPJS patients

Based on Table 2, it can be interpreted that 79% of the 62 respondents in medical services were satisfied with nursing services.

table, Next, Coding is changing the form of sentences or letters into numbers. Data entry is processed in the SPSS program, and the answers of each respondent are in the form of a code (numbers or letters) entered in a computer program or software. Finally, cleaning data must be checked again to see code errors, incompleteness, etc. The correction or cleaning is carried out.

C. Data analysis

Data analysis used a computer with the SPSS program, then statistical tests used the Chi-Square test. The analysis of the research data is univariate and bivariate. In this study, univariate analysis was carried out for each variable and the results of the study, namely the independent/free variable (medical care services) and the dependent/dependent variable (patient satisfaction), were analyzed using a frequency distribution table. In addition, a bivariate analysis was carried out to determine the correlation test between the independent variables, namely nursing services, and the dependent variable, namely. patient satisfaction. A Chi-square test with a significant level is used as this statistical test..

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Univariate analysis

The results of the univariate analysis yielded a frequency distribution of each category of independent variables (medical services, satisfaction) and the dependent variable (BPJS patient satisfaction) as follows:

a) Characteristics based on BPJS patient nursing services

In this study, nursing service variables were divided into two categories, namely good and bad. The frequency table is as follows:

c) Variables related to patient satisfaction concerning nursing services are as follows:

Nursing Services	Patient Satisfaction				Amount	%	ρ value	OR
	Satisfied	%	Not satisfied	%				
Well	42	84,0	8	16,0	50	100	0,038	3,750
Bad	7	58,3	5	41,7	12	100		
Total	55	77,4	13	57,7	62	100		

Table 3: The Relationship between Nursing Services and Outpatient BPJS Patient Satisfaction

Based on the statistical test results in Table 3, the ρ value = 0.038 indicates a significant relationship between medical services and patient satisfaction.

B. DISCUSSION

a) Nursing services for BPJS patients

Based on statistical analysis, it was found that 80.6% of the total 62 respondents had good nursing services.

Nursing services are core services for every patient's need, from which patients expect better and more efficient nursing services so that patients can feel comfortable and satisfied (Mubin and Jalal, 2014). Medical services that create patient satisfaction must meet the requirements and criteria of the nursing profession and, like health service providers, can provide quality services in accordance with expectations and goals to achieve satisfaction and meet patient expectations (Yani, 2007).

In line with research by Hartati et al (2011), the majority of respondents considered it good with a percentage of 86.5% of 45 respondents. According to Marpaung (2010) out of 39 respondents were satisfied with nursing services with a percentage of 68.4%. According to Purwanti (2017) where 72.2% get good service. Rustono (2019) good nursing services where the percentage is 96.7%. According to Fadilah (2019), it shows good service quality where the percentage is 64.9%.

The results of the research, theory, and research related to the researcher argue that excellent service given with conscience can lead to sincerity in work so that it can encourage service wholeheartedly, when the customer feels served, a feeling of being served arises so that the customer can interpret the service as good. Furthermore, if the service received by the customer is good, they are satisfied with the treatment, this can also help speed up recovery and the desire to come back when experiencing a relapse.

b) Outpatient BPJS patient satisfaction

The results of the analysis show that out of 62 respondents in nursing services, 79% are satisfied with the level of nursing services.

Patient satisfaction is the level of patient feelings obtained from the performance of health services received when patients compare it with their expectations (Imbalo, 2004). Meanwhile, according to Nursalam (2016), satisfaction is the capital gap between expectations (standards of service that should be) with the service that patients actually

receive. Customer satisfaction is the customer's response to the level of interest or customer expectations (expectations) before receiving service the service received (Muninjaya, 2011).

This is in line with Purwant research (2017), where the majority of 59.8% of respondents were satisfied with the level of service. Meanwhile, according to Rustono (2019), the patient satisfaction level was 95.6%. According to Fadilah (2019), the percentage of patient satisfaction is 55.4%. Purwati (2019) found that they were satisfied with the level of service a percentage of 59.8%.

From the results of research and theory as well as related research, the researcher's opinion arises where the various services provided to customers have gone well with various levels of service that can be felt by customers (patients). This can also provide a sense of satisfaction for service recipients.

c) Relationship between nursing services and BPJS patient satisfaction

The results of the statistical test analysis obtained the value of $\rho = 0.038$, so it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between nursing services and patient satisfaction.

Customer (patient) satisfaction arises when a need, desire, or expectation can be fulfilled when this expectation can be fulfilled with the service (health service) received by the patient who has the patient's expectations for the service (Supriyanto, 2010).

A person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment when comparing his impression of the effectiveness or results of a product or service that has or has not met his expectations before receiving the service (Nursalam, 2011).

Nursing is one of the professional health services which includes comprehensive services (biological, psychological, social, and spiritual) and is aimed at individuals, families, and communities who are sick or healthy (covering all processes of human life from birth to death) where the service is provided, carried out according to nursing knowledge (Kusnanto, 2004).

This is in line with Yeni's research (2012), where the statistical test results gave a value of $\rho = 0.007$ ($\rho > 0.05$), meaning that there is a significant relationship between service quality and patient satisfaction. According to Nurul Annisa (2017),

statistical results show a p-value of $0.000 \leq \alpha = 0.05$, which means there is a relationship between service quality and patient satisfaction. Nurhidayah (2019) The results obtained show that there is a relationship between nursing services and patient satisfaction using a statistical test score ($p=0.000$).

Meanwhile, according to Widyawati (2018) where there is a relationship between service quality and satisfaction levels, where the statistical test obtained a p-value = 0.005. According to Kartika (2020), there is a significant relationship between nursing services and the level of satisfaction, with the results of the statistical test p-value = $0.000 < 0.05$. Mohamad As'ad Efendy (2022) The results of the Spearman rho test analysis provide a p-value = 0.000 which is smaller than the alpha value (0.05), so it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected meaning that there is a relationship between service, quality and patient satisfaction. According to the statistical test results of Bahrudin (2022) ($p = 0.215; = 0.05$), there is a significant relationship between nursing service providers and customer satisfaction.

Based on research, theory, and related studies, researchers believe that there is a correlation between treatment performance and patient satisfaction. where this is a unit that cannot be separated because there are two aspects, there are those who provide services, there are those who receive, of course, these two are interconnected and can provide an assessment between the two.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and the specific objectives of discussing service analysis, it can be concluded as follows:

- Most of the patients rated nursing services as good out of a total of 62 respondents with a percentage value of 80.6%.
- Most of the patients who rated the level of patient satisfaction were 79.0% of a total of 62 respondents.
- There is a relationship between nurses and BPJS patient satisfaction with $p=0.038$ ($p < 0.05$).

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